

Worktext in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11

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ABSTRACT

This study involved 707 Grade 11 students and 16 English teachers from four secondary schools in the Bontoc I and II Districts, Division of Southern Leyte, during the academic year 2019–2020, and focused on the development of a Worktext in Reading Skills. It employed a descriptive quantitative research design using a survey questionnaire and a teacher-made proficiency test. The questionnaire determined the extent to which least-learned reading skills were developed, while the test measured students' proficiency levels. Data were analyzed using frequency count and mean. Findings revealed that students' achievement level was Satisfactory, with a mean

percentage score of 41.05%, indicating a need for improvement. All identified topics in English were found to be satisfactorily developed, while teaching approaches were only sometimes employed by teachers. Additionally, all cited problems were consistently experienced by teachers, suggesting persistent challenges in teaching reading skills. These results highlight the need for immediate and effective interventions to improve academic performance. The study concluded that students were at a Developing level in reading proficiency, emphasizing the necessity of designing and utilizing a Worktext in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11. It is recommended that teachers adopt Department of Education programs and implement varied strategies and interventions to enhance reading performance. Furthermore, well-planned lesson guides using diverse approaches should be utilized to effectively support students' reading development. Future studies in other divisions are also encouraged to validate these findings.

Keywords: *Reading proficiency, Worktext development, Grade 11 students, Instructional approaches, Southern Leyte*

INTRODUCTION

The essence of reading in the life of every individual has been underscored by Reading Specialists when they uttered that reading offers productive approach in skills development. In fact, it was the primary leisure activity during the time when there were no televisions and computers or any high technology gadgets. Reading is particularly geared towards the needs of Filipino students and designed to present the fundamental subject, English, in a new appealing way. It helps in mental development and is known to stimulate the muscles of the eyes, Smith (2016).

According to Hubbard (2017) high school students (with ages ranging from 12 to 17) already have a basic knowledge of English and the four communication skills which will enable them to function satisfactorily in certain English communication situations. The basic goal of high school English and of this worktext is to enhance the students' knowledge and skills so that they can function effectively in any situation which requires the use of reading. They need to be able to express themselves in speech and in writing. They need to think independently, critically, and creatively. Hence, they should be given opportunities to enhance higher order thinking skills like analysis and evaluation, Maker (2018).

This instructional material is holistic and transformative. It focuses on the students; it is student-friendly. Discovery learning develops dynamics minds. Students are presented with experiences that lead to meaning and understanding.

Worktext in reading skills development as an ultimate output this study gives impact and geared towards the needs of the students and designed to help improve the poor reading proficiency of the Grade 11 students in secondary schools in Southern Leyte, Division. These reading skills developments include topics from first grading to fourth grading period like reading comprehension activities, writing reaction paper, writing concept paper and writing position paper and report. This material assists student to improve their comprehension skills through developing their higher order thinking skills or HOTS ability.

Fernando (2005), discussed reading as a communicative perspective through which new languages are acquired. It is a holistic approach in reading by organizing them around compelling contemporary themes. Reading as communicative competence is the primary goal to which comprehension is developed among students.

This research aimed to give a comprehensive knowledge of the nature and scope on reading development of the Grade 11 students designed to enhance instructional activities in reading and writing that would raise the proficiency level of the students.

Baker, (2007) pointed out that in schools the students should be encouraged to read more books or programmed materials so that the reading level of the learners will become higher. The poor results of the proficiency level of students who are not using the programmed materials or any instructional materials will affect the educational foundation of the learners. It means that teachers should look into the different activities which would help students to actively involve in the different lessons and engage them in different activities so they can practice the appropriate skills of the subject. The teachers must apply their knowledge

of the different methods and techniques to teaching. Kim, (2007) said that the true backbone of most learners is to introduce reading in English and is to improve the proficiency level of students in the English and Filipino subjects. If a student's reading ability is poor then, chances of his performance in other courses will be compromised. Furthermore, teachers must pay attention to the needs of the learners in order to increase and improve the reading level of the students in the subject. Apparently, these skills in English for Grade 11 are very important in connection with our daily routine activities as these cover people, and the physical world where we live in. Acquiring and applying these skills and concepts is one of the responsibilities of the school as the center for learning in our society as well as the teachers. Teaching reading is one of the five micro skills in the Grade 11 and the teacher must base his materials and procedures on the psychological foundation if he is to succeed in making experiential learning a dynamic one. Reading is the instrument which the students employ in thinking and reasoning. His deficiency of the English skills will greatly affect the learning process.

Indeed the K-12 secondary English language curriculum seeks to develop citizenship and to address the communication needs like interpersonal, informative and aesthetic of Filipino students, which is emerging as the international lingua franca. In line with the development is applied linguistics and pedagogy, and in consonance with the government's thrust and globalization, this emerging English curriculum adopts a communicative, interactive, collaborative approach to learning as well as reflection and aim of developing language learners aware of and able to cope with global trends.

Rebecca, (2009) found significant differences in the performance level of the learners. The first group was provided with programmed materials, worktexts, and other instructional materials. They increased their comprehension and performance level in English while the second group who did not use any instructional material had the poor results in their comprehension and proficiency level. Thus, instructional materials, worktexts, books, and programmed text are recommended for use in any subject offered by the department of education in all year levels.

Banzuela, (2005) supports this idea when he explained that worktext; instructional materials play an important role in the teaching and learning process. Observation shows that English teachers, despite the demands made by the Department of Education on the maximum use of the interactive, cooperative, collaborative learning, and integrated strategies, still hang on to traditional methods of teaching like the use of lecture method, textbook method, question-answer procedure. Teachers should look into the different activities which would facilitate the active involvement of the students throughout the lessons and encourage them in such a way that they can practice their skills in English.

The idea of Goldschmidt (2012) is supported by worktext specialists when they said that a worktext is an alternative resource material to supplement textbooks being used by teachers. Worktext is a new concept in the presentation of textual materials and that the text is custom- designed to the different valuable insights presented shed light on the conduct of the study. Hence this study exactly fit the needs of each student.

Statement of the Problem

The main objective of this study was to design worktext in reading skills development for Grade 11 in the three public secondary schools in the Division of Southern, Leyte during the school year 2019 - 2020.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the proficiency level of the Grade 11 students in English?
 2. To what extent are the following least learned competencies in English developed among the Grade 11 students:
 - 2.1 Decoding Meaning of Words Through Dictionary/ Context Clues
 - 2.2 Following Directions/ Instruction
 - 2.3 Noting Details
 - 2.4 Getting the Main Idea
 - 2.5 Reading Comprehension
 - 2.6 Predicting Outcomes
 - 2.7 Differentiating Fact from Opinion
 - 2.8 Evaluating Ideas/ Making Generalization
 - 2.9 Drawing Conclusions
 - 2.10 Using the Library Effectively
 - 2.11 Skimming and Scanning
 3. To what extent are the following identified instructional Materials used by teachers in teaching Reading English for Grade 11?
 - 3.1 Printed materials
 - 3.2 Audio Aids
 - 3.3 Visual Aids
 - 3.4 Audio- Visual aids
 - 3.5 Demonstration
 - 3.6 Community resource
 - 3.7 Laboratory
 - 3.8 Programmed instruction
 4. To what extent are the following identified approaches used by Teachers in teaching English for Grade 11?
 - 4.1 Process approach
 - 4.2 Discovery approach
 - 4.3 Experimental approach
 - 4.4 Cooperative approach
 5. What are the problems met by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11?
 6. What worktext in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11 may be developed on the findings of the study?
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Theoretical Framework

A well- developed and constructed worktext in reading skills presents a number of opportunities to teachers for learning and is rooted or anchored in a process approach to teaching and learning. It enables teachers to focus on important learning goals in the domain, centering their attention on what the student will learn rather than what the student will do. Haston (2007), discussed process approach as learning by constructing meaning through interacting with and intercepting their environment. The meaning of what individuals learn is coupled with their life experiences and contexts; it is constructed by the learners, not by the teachers; and learning is anchored in the context of real-life situation and problems. It challenges the technical-rational approach to education by redefining the relationship between the knower and what is known, including what is most worth knowing and who decides. And the potential benefits to teacher understanding of how learning develops in a domain, how ideas within the domain are inter-related, how instructional planning and formative assessment can be mapped into the development and ensure the worth of investment and that our students deserve no less.

On the theory of social cognition Borko (2006), states that the discovery approach to learning is more than just the individual construction of knowledge. Interactions with others in learners' social environments are major factors influencing what is learned and that learning takes place. Over time, individuals participate in a number of different social communities that provide the cognition tools for them sense of their experiences. This study further adopted the eclectic approach to reading which is supposed to supply the need of the learners for cooperation approach in learning how to read effectively and meaningfully.

Davis (2008) refers to this gap between what is known and what is being learned as the Zone of Proximal Development, and he stresses the importance of the social interaction between the students and someone who is more skilled and tasks being learned. As they strive to attain learning goal, students draw upon their previous experiences and build upon existing knowledge. They find meaning in the entire learning process by learning subject in an integrated, multi-disciplinary manner and in appropriate contexts. The ideal connection process would be three-fold (1) student review what they already know related to the new concept; (2) they learned about and practice the new concepts; (3) they tie what they have learned to a real-life scenario.

In another development, cognitively based views of reading comprehension emphasize the interactive nature of reading and the constructive nature of comprehension. Dole (2010) stated, experimental approach, besides knowledge brought to bear on the reading process, a set of flexible, adaptable strategies are used to make sense of a text and monitor ongoing understanding. Thus he conceived ideas on several levels of thinking and, while conceptualizes he learns to associate, correlate, organized and evaluate ideas linearly and globally. Furthermore, advocates of this method use reading and other communication skills such as listening, speaking and writing together in the instructional program. It uses a listing of language experiences which generate productive thinking, allow freedom of expression, satisfy curiosity and promote personal satisfaction to the extent that learning becomes a lifelong experience which requires ever- maturing and more complex skills and knowledge in reading critically. Graves (2011) stressed that developing reading skills would take a lot of process before an individual can comprehend a text.

The researcher strongly believes that it needs worktext in reading skills development in teaching to conceptualize, associate, correlate and organize ideas. As a worktext specialist singled out that the development of reading skills needs a worktext in order to help the students maximize their learning.

The worktext specialists further stressed that in the preparation of the worktext in reading skills development to teaching and learning begins with specific objective statements and ends with a summary of key words, main concepts and overview exercises. These features enable students to test themselves on their comprehension of the material. As such, the worktext in reading skills development may be used as a self-study instructional material. Barlett (2017) believed that the material being read is more important to the process than the person who reads the material.

In the concept of development, it emphasizes that the teaching in reading is conceptual in nature. The reader is developmentally exposed to divergent ideas and ideals that call for mental synthesis and abstraction. Thus, he is trained to conceive ideas on different levels of thinking and, while conceptualizing he learns to associate, correlate, organizes and evaluates ideas clearly and globally.

The reading act then becomes for the readers a synergic relationship, which implies a divergent relationship. Convergent relationship produces a new set of relation, at times differing from the original form or model. The basic source of understanding the concept's correlates is the child's own experiential and maturational background in language development.

The above-mentioned theories are relevant to the study as they are the bases in the preparation of the worktext in reading skills development for Grade 11 students.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

The conceptual framework of the study lays out the key factors, constructs variables and presumes relationships among them. In this study the conceptual framework employed the commonly used ITO model or the Input, Thru-put and Output model.

The Input. This includes the proficiency level of the Grade 11 students in Reading of Bontoc I and II, Southern Leyte Division.

The Thru-put. This includes the input and data so with the information of Worktext in Reading Skills Development to its components in terms of the reading skills of the Grade 11 students such as decoding meaning of words through dictionary/ context clues, following directions/ instructions, noting details, getting the main idea, reading comprehension, predicting outcomes, differentiating facts from opinion, evaluating ideas/making generalization, drawing conclusions, using the library effectively, and skimming and scanning; and the learning designs in terms of Process Approach, Discovery Approach, Experimental Approach, and Cooperative Approach.

The Output. This is the outcome of the study. The results of the skills developed among students and strategies utilized by the teachers that provide the ultimate objective of the study which is designing Worktext in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11.

Figure 1. Schematic Presentation of the Conceptual Framework of the Study.

Significance of the Study

Quality Education is given to meet the needs and aspirations of individuals in the society. In this study, the researcher shares some innovative learning activities to students, teachers and future researchers.

Specifically, this study would be beneficial to the following:

Students. This Worktext in Reading Skills Development is a communicative-based instructional material that would help students to enhance their skills and abilities specifically on the reading aspects. They would also be able to identify their strong and weak points in learning English specifically in reading. They will be encouraged to learn to read, and study independently using the worktext in reading skills development.

Teachers. The Worktext in Reading Skills Development would be one of their teaching material in addition to other material with proper guidance, students may use this Worktext independently.

The output would also serve as additional guide to the teachers' so that they can make other instructional materials in Reading.

Future Researchers. Through this study, the researcher would be able to conceptualize and draw insight into problems that need further studies. This study may provide a better clue towards the solution of some problems.

The Worktext in Reading Skills Development is important, necessary and essential to the researcher as it would serve as reference guide in teaching English. The study would also serve one of their related studies.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study focused on designing Worktext in Reading Skills Development for the Grade 11 students. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the proficiency level of the Grade 11 students in English as perceived by the teachers in terms of decoding meaning of words through dictionary/ context clues, following directions/ instructions, noting details, getting the main idea, reading comprehension, predicting outcomes, differentiating fact from opinion, evaluating ideas/ making generalization, drawing conclusions, using the library effectively, and skimming and scanning. The teaching approaches utilized by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11 students; along Process Approach, Discovery Approach Experimental Approach, and Cooperative Approach.

The instructional procedures undertaken in the developmental learning design through rationale, objectives, pre-test, learning approaches, developmental learning exercise, progress check, feedback in progress check and evaluation; and determined the problems met by the teachers in teaching Reading for Grade 11. Hence, this served as the bases in determining the Worktext in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11 that were developed.

This study was conducted in the four public secondary school in Bontoc I and II Districts in the Division of Sothern Leyte. The schools were Bontoc National High School, Divisoria National High School, Hilaan National High School, and Paku National High School, in Bontoc Southern Leyte.

The respondents of the study were the Grade 11 students and teachers teaching English in Bontoc I and II Districts in Southern Leyte Division. A total of seven hundred seven students and sixteen English teachers who were involved in this study and were conducted during the academic year 2019-2020.

Definition of Terms

The researchers consider it necessary to define some terms which were used in this study to facilitate understanding so as to help the reader better understand the concepts covered in the study.

Comprehension. Ability to understand, the act or action of grasping with the intellect; the capacity for understanding fully, Morgan (2015) As used in this study, the term refers to the ability of the Grade 11 students to grasp with intellectual or capacity to understand fully on the printed materials they read.

Critical Reading. This term refers to the process of identifying and understanding the meaning of the characters and words in written or printed material. (Dictionary) An interpretation or understanding of a situation or of something that has been written.

Worktext. The term refers to a self-learning kit which usually consists of package of learning activities that have to be accomplished by the student, Hubbard (2017). In this study the output of the study which covers from first quarter to fourth quarter which includes selections and comprehension questions for activities especially intended to practice and improve students' proficiency level.

Reading Skills Development. used to extend and strengthen a child's reading abilities. It also provides students with instructional support before, during, and after reading. The teacher takes an active role as he or she prepares students to read the text by pre-teaching important vocabulary, eliciting prior knowledge, teaching students how to use a specific reading skill, and providing a purpose for reading, (<http://www.educ.com>). In this study, the teacher provides direct instruction in one or more word-recognition or comprehension skill in order to extend and strengthen the reading abilities of the Grade 11 students.

English II. The term refers as the language, literature, or writing as a subject of study, (<http://www.readingrockets.org/helping/target/vocabulary>). As used in this study, the term refers to the subject offered in the school that was considered as the second language of the students.

Reading. This term refers to the process of identifying and understanding the meaning of the characters and words in written or printed material, Brittel (2010). An interpretation or understanding of a situation or of something that has been written.

Reading Activities. The state of being active, behavior or action of a particular kind, something that is done as work or for a particular purpose, and something that is done for pleasure and that usually involves a group of people, Bustus (2016). As used in this study, the term refers to an instructional device that would serve as teaching device as an aid in teaching language skills in the grade 11 students.

Evaluating Ideas Explicitly or Implicitly. One of the reading comprehension strategies and is concisely defined as “making judgments”, Rumelhart (2016). Hence, it is a complex strategy that includes; determining importance of information in written text; determining accuracy and credibility; determining appropriateness and/or usefulness; determining personal enjoyment of a text; and determining one’s own progress as a reader.

Least- Learned Skills. The term refers to the skills in every concept or skills enumerated or listed in the Curriculum Guide that have the most number of errors committed by the Grade 11 students in every academic year, (<http://teachervision.fen.com/skill-builder/reading-comprehension/48779.html>.) This will indicate content and performance standard, together with the learning competency that learners should meet in order for them to meet the content standard and performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Related Literature

Man has to learn the reading process in order to become literate and interpret ideas, symbols pictures and the like. As a reader the student has to comprehend on the literal level by remembering details. Later he has to move to the interpretative level by looking beyond the stated message. At the applied level, he has to learn to make a wide use of his accumulated knowledge by reacting, reflecting, and analyzing. Understanding the steps, skills, and techniques of the reading process will help him gain insights, sophistication, and productivity of an able reader and thinker. Headly (2015)

Reading has three-stage process. Each stage contains with the material, activating the student’s schema (skeleton of knowledge on the subject), and setting goals for learning. While reading, the student must integrate knowledge by predicting, picturing, relating, monitoring, and correcting. After reading he has to recall and to retain information and learn by reviewing, relating, organizing and reacting. To operate at the Metacognitive level (with an awareness of the thinking process task) the student must know the process involved in reading and be able to regulate them to know about his own knowing.

In another development, Graves (2016) presented the contemporary and concept view of the reading process. He underscored that the cognitive- constructivist view of reading emphasizes that the reading is a process in which the reader actively searches for meaning in what he or she reads. This view also emphasizes that this search for meaning depends very heavily on the reader’s having an existing store of knowledge or schemata that he or she draws on in that search for meaning, and that the active contribution of the researcher is significant enough to justify the assertion that the reader actually constructs the meaning he or she arrives at. The following three topics describe three key components of the cognitive constructivist model- the cognitive orientation, schemata, and construct.

Graves (2016) explains that the cognitive orientation is the earliest and strongest influence behind this view and it comes from cognitive psychology. The Psychological orientation became the main point of view of American psychology. Cognitive psychology can perhaps be best understood in comparison with

behaviorism, which was dominant psychological orientation in the United States for many years, and which had a huge effect on the reading instruction of that period and continues to have some influence today.

Graves (2016) further explains that Behavioral psychologist viewed people as rather passive respondents to their environment and gave little attention to the mind and its role in learning. In the behaviorist view, reading was rather a passive process in which the information on a page of text was somehow absorbed by the reader as her eyes scanned the pages. Later, behaviorism began to be replaced by the cognitive orientation.

On other hand, cognitive psychologists view the mind as central to learning and the study of learners' thought processes as a central focus of their work. They also viewed learners as active participants, who act on rather than simply respond to their external environment as they learn. In the cognitive view, reading is very much an active process in which the meaning, the readers glean from the text, is heavily influenced by the cognitive work that he puts into the reading process. Both the beginning reader- who we might observe carefully sounding out words, and the accomplished reader, who appears to be effortlessly absorbing the contents of the material being read- are in fact actively engaged in making meaning from the text.

The concept of schema, the second influence on the view of the reading process described here, is closely related to the cognitive orientation. In fact, schema theory is one of the central concepts of cognitive psychology. Schema theory is concerned with knowledge, particularly with the way knowledge is represented in their minds and the importance of prior knowledge to learning something new. As described by the theory, knowledge is package in organized structure termed schema.

According to Rumelhart (2016), schemata constitute our knowledge about objects situations, events, sequences of events, actions, and sequences of actions". Individuals have schemata for objects such as house, for situations such as being in class, for events such as getting up- eating- showering and going to work. They interpret their experiences- whether these experiences are direct encounters with the world or various experiences gained through reading- by comparing and in most cases matching those experiences to an existing schema. In other words, individuals make sense of what they read and of their experiences more generally. Our schemata are related to each other and constitute a vast and elaborate network of interrelationships. The more we know about something, the easier it will be deal with that topic and learn more about it schemata assist the reader in initially making sense of what he or she reads, relating information newly acquired to prior knowledge, determining the relative importance of information in a text, making inferences, and remembering.

According to Anderson (2016), constructivism influenced the view of the reading process and has many roots and many branches being in fact a philosophical, political, and social construction as well as a psychological one. Here, we use the term in its psychological sense. Used in this sense, constructivism serves to emphasize a point and emphasizes the fact that comprehending a text is a very active and constructive process.

Consider this metaphor of the constructivism view of reading. The author of a text, like the architect who draws a blueprint, has created a representation of her ideas. The reader, like the builder, must take this

representation and construct something. Much like the builder must construct a house, the reader must construct meanings. Constructivists often use the phrase “making meaning” to emphasize the readers in active role in comprehending texts. Students cannot just passively absorb meaning from the texts. A truly passive reading would leave the reader simply having turned the pages. Instead, readers must have actively engaged with the text. Consider what they are reading, and link the information they are gleaned from the text, with ideas, topics, and events they already know. Moreover, the more difficult text becomes for students- the more new and challenging information it presents- the more actively engaged readers must be.

In addition, to emphasize the active nature of reading, constructivism adds a new point to the view of the reading process outlined here: The meaning one constructs from a text is subjective, the result of that particular reader’s processing of the text. Just as no two builders will construct exactly the same house from a blueprint, so no two readers will construct exactly the same meaning from the text. A particular reader’s processing is influenced by the sum total of the reader’s experience as well as by his unique intellectual makeup. Because of this, each reader constructs a somewhat different interpretation of the text, the text as he conceptualizes it.

Having noted that constructivism emphasizes the subjectivity of the meaning, it is also important to note that different texts differ dramatically in how much they constrain meaning. An abstract poem may prompt many appropriate interpretations. While a manual on how to install some new software should prompt only one. Returning to the blueprint metaphor, one might describe the abstract poem as a sketch the author has drawn, while the computer manual is a very detailed plan. In between these two extremes, lie a range of texts that invite various degrees of individual interpretation.

Ultimately, constructivism is a social construct as well as a psychological one. Most constructivist emphasize that the social world which we live heavily influences the meaning that we derive from our experiences, including our experiences with text, thus, constructivism strongly supports the inclusion of a variety of sorts of discussion and group work as part of reading and learning.

To sum up, the cognitive-constructivism view of reading process conceives of the reader as an active engaged participant who uses a variety of sorts of prior knowledge and frequently interacts with others as he or she constructs meaning from the text.

There are three concepts that extend constructivist view of the reading process namely: the interactive model of reading, automaticity, and metacognition.

The Interactive Model of Reading. The interactive model of reading schema theory emphasizes the importance of the reader’s knowledge in understanding a text. The interactive model of reading, on the other hand, serves as a reminder that both the reader and the text play important roles in reading. Interactive models can perhaps be best understood what contrasted to what have been called “bottom-up” and “top-down” models. Bottom-up models assume that the text is singularly important and that the reader processes text by first recognizing lower-level units. In this view, the reader might first perceive letters, then

synthesize several letters to form words, then synthesize several words to form a phrase, and so on. Processing operates in a single direction- from the text to the reader.

Top-down models are just the opposite of the bottom-up models. The top-down models assume that the reader is singularly important and processes text by first hypothesizing about the content of the text and then selectively sampling the text to confirm or disconfirm her hypothesis. In this view, the reading process begins with the highest-level units, for example words, only to a limited extent. Again processing operates in a single direction- but in the top- down perspective that view is from the reader to the text.

As described by the interactive model, processing is neither exclusively top-down nor exclusively bottom- up. Instead, the reader arrives at understanding of a text by simultaneously, synthesizing information from a variety of sources. These include word-level knowledge, syntactic knowledge, and various sorts of schema he or she has internalized.

Good readers need to rely appropriately on the texts they are reading and their background knowledge to arrive at meaning, and they need to work with the sorts of texts and tasks that facilitate their doing so. For example, repeatedly giving students' selections that deal with large unfamiliar topics and that include a lot of difficult vocabulary may force them to give un attention to the individual words they encounter, to neglect summoning up their prior knowledge to bear on their understanding of the text.

Conversely, having students only read silently and providing no follow-up to what they need or having them repeatedly engage in post-reading discussion that are vaguely related to what they read may encourage students to give too little attention to the text itself.

At this point, we should note a qualification regarding the interactive model. It has to do with what has been called modular processing. In somewhat the same way that conceiving of reading as an interactive process acts as a caution against overemphasizing the role of schema-driven or top- down processing in reading, the concept of modularity acts as a caution against over generalizing the extent to what is reading is an interactive process.

La Berge (2015), the concept of automaticity is both a crucial concept and a straight forward one. The automatic activity is one that we can perform instantly and with very little attention. Pointed out in their pioneering work automaticity in reading, the mind's attention capacity is severely limited: in fact, we can only attend to about one thing at a time. If we are faced with a task in which we are forced to attend to too many things at once, we will fail. For example, a number of people have reached a level of automaticity in driving a stick shift car. They can automatically push in the clutch, let up on the accelerator, shift gears, let out the clutch, and press on the accelerator, and they can do all this while driving in rush hour traffic. Beginning drivers cannot do all this at once; they have not yet automated the various sub-processes, and it would be foolish dangerous for them to attempt to drive a stick shift car in an attention-demanding situation such as rush hour traffic. He further stresses out that reading includes a number of sub-processes that need to take place at the same time- processes such as recognizing words, assigning meanings to words, constructing the meaning of sentences and larger units, and relating the information gleaned from the text to inform we already have. Unless some of these processes are automated, readers simply cannot do all of

this at once. Specifically, readers need to perform two processes automatically; they need to recognize words automatically, and they need to assign meanings to words automatically. For example, if a student is reading and come across the word imperative, he or she needs to automatically recognize the word and automatically- immediately and without conscious attention- know that it means “absolutely necessary”. If the learner needs to pause very often and go through some sort of mental process to recognize and assign meanings to words, reading will be difficult and laborious, and the student will not understand much of what he or she is reading. This problem can be particularly acute for learners for whom English is a language. In addition to going through the processes, that native speaker do, nonnative speakers may need to translate English into their own language in the process of arriving at meaning. Thus, becoming automatic in processing words is extremely important for ESL students.

Fortunately, the road to automaticity is very straight one in order to become automatic at an activity, one needs to practice the activity a lot in non-taxing situations. To become automatic in reading, students need to do a lot of reading in materials they find relatively easy, understandable, interesting, and enjoyable; and they need to do that reading in situations that are non-taxing, that is, in situations in which they can read for information and enjoyment and not be faced with difficult questions or other requirements based on the reading. In brief, students need to be given ample opportunity to read independently in material they find interesting, enjoyable, and relatively easy.

Flavel (2014), metacognition refers to one’s knowledge concerning one’s own cognitive process and products or anything related to them: with respect to reading metacognition refers to the reader’s awareness of his or her comprehension of text as he or she is reading it and to the reader’s regulation on the processes that lead to comprehension. Metacognitive readers have the ability to mentally step outside of themselves and view themselves as learners faced with particular learning tasks. In particular, accomplished readers have metacognitive knowledge about themselves, the reading task they face, and the strategies they can employ in completing these tasks. Active awareness of one’s comprehension while reading and the ability to use effective fix up strategies when comprehension breaks down, are absolutely essential to becoming an effective reader.

Indeed, the use of a worktext as an approach in teaching reading permits students to work at different rates by presenting simple concept units of study to construct learning expressions of any needed magnitude and content coverage. Worktext provides students with immediate feedback so they can determine whether they have achieved mastery. The instruction is to extent that, it adjusts to learners’ differences. Individualizing instruction has been received as a key component of instructional effectiveness.

Good (2010), stressed that the use of worktext as an approach in teaching has been widely accepted as described pedagogical practice, its utilization in classroom leaves much to be desired. He further stressed that instructional worktext is a package it integrated material or an identified and related set and sequence of learning activities that provides systematic guidance through particular learning experience as specific program.

Lardizabal (2012), pointed out that worktext modules have many advantages for the students and for the teachers. For the students they have to work at their own, they assume responsibility for learning,

they find that textbooks are not the only sources of learning; they know exactly what they have learned. For teachers, they have time to correct individual learning problems, they can identify problems earlier, they are free to serve as resource person to answer questions, and to help those who need guidance, and there is a better cooperation between teachers and students.

Butts (2017) further strengthened and stated that the development of worktext as the instructional materials must be mindful of the need to include in their materials; the discussion and definition that are appropriate both the student who is capable of and not of using formal reasoning pattern as well. He disclosed that the basic characteristic of a good worktext module as self-contained that its content would allow students to work independently by himself with minimum assistance from the teacher, and self-paced where students achieve different levels at given periods such as that one can finish ahead of others who are fairly catching up, and still others are training behind. Topic or subject matter should be that enough and well defined, it should be adequately motivating; it should provide opportunities for interaction with the students. Its objectives and activities should be properly sequenced. It should be written in a clear correct language suitable to the level of learner; and it should be accurate.

Ultimately, the review of related literature provided the researcher rich ideas on how to construct or design the instrument and the process used in the study.

Related Studies

Several researches related to the present study were reviewed. They are the following:

Acero, (2016) conducted a study on The Effect of Programmed Instruction in the Teaching of Transformation Grammar to the Freshmen Education Students. Findings revealed that the difference in achievement is highly significant between the experimental and control groups, hence programmed activities in reading in teaching transformation grammar proved to be more effective than the traditional method. She also made a programmed test in reading for fresh men students. The material was tested to the students and closed monitoring was implemented so that they will understand the mechanics to the fullest. Upon finishing the program, the students were given reading materials to get their reactions on the programmed learning materials. After revisions were done, the material was tried again to a group of six different students with different reading levels who were randomly selected to determine if the reading materials were workable. It was concluded that other students were slow, some were average and fast learners and it was a highly recommended as a method of acquiring knowledge in reading.

This study has similarities with the present study on the content area which is English. They differ however, on the locale of the study, the output of the study and respondents of the study.

Avila, (2012) developed A Reinforcement Instructional Module in Filipino for Grade V pupils of Libertad Elementary School Palo, Leyte for academic year 2009-2010. Her study revealed that the instructional module was easy and interesting to the students and found the learning materials a highly motivated method of acquiring knowledge and skills.

The study of Avila was similar with the present study. Both studies adopted the descriptive research method in the development of the instructional module. She focused on the preparation of instructional

module in Filipino for Grade V students. The difference is that, the present study deals with the used of Worktext in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11.

A certain study was conducted by Sajonia, (2011) of the Philippine Normal University, regarding Programmed Text in English designed to develop other reading skills. The result of the investigation disclosed that the students who were taught using the traditional method of teaching were not active learners.

This present study is similar to Sajonia's research since both used descriptive methods of design. However, its differences; defers on the respondents of the study and the grade level. Sajonia's study focused in the Grade 2 pupils while the present study is in Grade 11.

Tejares, (2016) conducted a study on the Development of a Programmed Learning Package for Self-improvement for High School Students. Her study revealed that the respondents would like to have informative materials on how decisions are made and how to arrive at good decisions. Its similarities is that, both used programmed for learning development for the students. While its differences is that, Tejares focused on the Grade 7 students, while the present study focused on the senior high school students particularly the Grade 11 students reading skills development.

It was concluded that a readable and relevant material could be developed to meet the needs of the users if the program text is based on their needs and if they consider the topics to be taught to the students.

Cuartel, (2015) developed a Programmed Text in Human Behavior in an Organization which could be utilized as instructional material for Master in Education students. She utilized descriptive research method to find out the specific topic perceived to be difficult. This present study was similar to Cuartel's research hence both studies used descriptive type of research and used program text instructional materials; while its differences is that, the present study used the Grade 11 as the respondents of the study while Cuartel's study used the Master in Education students.

Similarly, Reforzado, (2011) aimed at Developing Instructional Materials for English 6 Reading Comprehension in Burauen South District. The result of the study was that the reading level of Grade 6 students of Burauen South District was on the average level which implied that the students need more inputs in terms of learning experiences. The teachers could not fully attain the instructional objectives and the expected competencies that ought to be developed among the children. It was concluded in that the instructional materials available to Grade 6 classes were not enough to meet the learning needs of the students. This was due to the high cost of the instructional materials and the ample time needed for the preparation of the instructional materials.

This study has similarity with the present study on the content area which is English. They differ however, on the target users of the programmed materials. She developed the programmed instruction for the elementary school while the present study was based on the worktext in reading skills development for Grade 11.

Regis, (2010) developed a "Work text in Reading Skills Development for Kindergarten." The study was conducted in Tacloban City Division to the 27 Preparatory Schools. The findings of the study showed that there was a need for mastery of English skills, like instructional materials, work text and workbooks.

This study has similarity with the present study on the content area which is English. They differ however, on the target users of the programmed materials. Regis developed the work text in reading skills for the kindergarten school while the present study was based on the worktext in reading skills development for Grade 11.

Cabelin's, (2009) study was on "Building Strategies in Vocabulary Development for Grade II: Achievements Integration Techniques." This study was conducted in Jaro I and II Districts. Among the problems met were lack of parent's follow-up and insufficient instructional materials like workbooks and work text. One of conclusions mentioned that there is a need to provide supplemental materials for teachers' use in vocabulary.

The study of Cabelin and the present study have similarities in the sense that both studies employed descriptive method of research and the output of the study was the improvement of the performance of the target users. Both studies focused on the English subject. They differ however; because Cabelin's study was intended for Grade II students while the present study is intended for the Grade 11 students.

Kempis, (2013) of Asian Development Foundation College developed "Lesson Guides on Oral Language Skills Development in English for Second Year High School." This study was conducted in the secondary public schools in the Municipality of Abuyog, Leyte, Leyte Division. Findings revealed that the teachers who were teaching English subject were in dire need of the lesson guides who would help developed the oral language skills among the learners.

The study of Kempis and the present study have similarities in the sense that both studies employed descriptive method of research and the output of the study was the improvement of the performance in reading of the target users. Likewise, both studies focused on the English subject. Their difference is that, Kempis' research used the Grade 8 students as the respondents of the study, while the present study used the Grade 11 students as the respondents of the study.

Renomeron, (2011) developed a "Programmed text for Grade I in Reinforcement and Enrichment Activities on Reading Comprehension." The study was conducted in Burauen North and South District to the Grade I students and teachers. Findings revealed that the performance level of the Grade I students in English was low.

Both studies used programmed text for reading enrichment activities. And study of Renomeron was conducted in two districts in Burauen while the present study is intended for Grade 11 students on Work text in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11 in the secondary schools in the Division of Southern Leyte.

Romero, (2011) developed a programmed text on Human Behavior in Organization which could be utilized as instructional material for master in Management Students. She utilized descriptive research method to find out the specific topic perceived to be difficult and of functional interests to students, and adopted convenience sampling procedure in conducting the study.

This study has a relation to the present study because they have the same purposed. The problems met revealed were lack of parent's follow-up and insufficient instructional materials like workbooks/work text. One of conclusions mentioned that there is a need to provide supplemental materials for teachers' use in vocabulary development for Grade 5. However, they differ on the Grade level and the scope of

respondents of the study. Romero's study was conducted to the Grade 5 pupils in Jaro District, Leyte Division while the present is for Grade 11 students. The review of related studies provided the researcher with rich information relative to the development of the Worktext in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11. This shows that successful reading instructions should go with the proper use of instructional tool like worktext particularly in developing reading comprehension. Most of the studies reviewed centered on the development of instructional materials as supplementary guide to teachers in improving reading abilities of the students in any level of education. Ultimately, the review of related literature and studies provided the researcher rich ideas and information on how to construct the output of the study, Worktext in Reading Skills Development.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the descriptive type of research. Which determined the proficiency level in reading of the Grade 11 students; determined the extent to which the following competences are taught and developed by the Grade 11 teachers, identified instructional materials and approaches used by the teachers and determined the choice of reading materials designed to give information and pleasure and to develop appreciation for reading, and develop strategies for coping with unknown words and ambiguous sentence structures and discourse; decoding meaning of words through dictionary/ context clues; following directions/ instructions; noting details; getting the main idea; reading comprehension; predicting outcomes; differentiating fact from opinion; evaluating ideas/ making generalization; drawing conclusions; using library effectively; and skimming and scanning; the strategies utilized and analyzed the skills that were found least- learned by the Grade 11 students in the 4 respective schools in the Division of Southern Leyte; and served as the bases for the development of worktext in reading skills development is designed in such a way that it would provide the students with the skills, techniques, and procedures necessary to enter this highly competitive field of performance in school. It addresses the importance of reading and how to communicate effectively to various groups. Each part of the worktext is self-contained and can be taught as a separate unit to fit individual class or student needs. Explanations are concise and streamlined and are followed by a model skill practice exercise. The comprehension questions reflect the literal, interpretative, and applied levels of reading; vocabulary development strategies have corresponding exercises which are presented in the worktext, and each selection is followed by a generous number of skill development questions, comprehension both multiple choice and true or false, short answer questions to encourage critical thinking.

Fraenkel (2010), descriptive research defines as comparing to sets of data from pre to post result. Pretest result shows data without using materials in teaching while posttest result shows data after using the materials develop in the study like the enhancement, instructional activities in reading for the Grade 11 students of Paku National High School, Hilaan National High School, Divisoria National High School and Bontoc National High School all from the Division of Southern, Leyte.

The data gathered was collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics thus the analysis of the data would provide the researcher basis in developing worktext in reading skills development for Grade 11.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in the four (4) National High School in the Division of Southern, Leyte namely: Paku National High School, Hilaan National High School and Bontoc National High School during the academic year 2019-2020. Both schools is run by a school principal and not less than 20 members of the teaching force and 4 school personal staff These secondary schools have its own buildings equipped with facilities that can accommodate the population of the school.

Figure 2 shows the Map of Southern Leyte which shows the Secondary Schools involved in the study.

Figure 2. Map of Southern Leyte showing the locale of the study.

Respondent of the study

The respondents of the study were the Grade 11 students and teachers teaching English in Bontoc I and II Districts in Southern Leyte Division. A total of seven hundred seven (707) Grade 11 students and sixteen (16) teachers were completely enumerated and were involved in the study.

Table 1 Presents the Grade 11 student-respondents.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents of the Study

Respondents Schools	Student Respondents	Teacher Respondents
1. Paku National High School	215	5
2. Hilaan National High School	134	3
3. Divisoria National High School	123	3
4. Bontoc National High School	235	5
TOTAL	707	16

Table 1, shows the total number of the Grade 11 student respondents; Paku National High School has a total of two hundred fifteen student respondents and has five English teacher respondents. Hilaan National High School has a total of one hundred thirty-four student respondents and has three English teachers. Divisoria National High School has a total of one hundred twenty-three student respondents and has three teacher respondents. And Bontoc National High School has a total of two hundred thirty-five student respondents and has five English teachers.

A total of seven hundred seven student respondents and sixteen teacher respondents from the four secondary schools in Southern Leyte Division.

Research Instrument

The Researcher utilized two research instruments. These were the teacher- made proficiency test and the survey questionnaire for teacher- respondents.

Teacher- Made Proficiency Test. The teacher-made proficiency test was composed of two parts. Part I elicits personal information of the respondents which includes name of the students and name of the school. And in order to determine and measure the reading ability and skills of the students, Part II focuses on the proficiency level in English of the Grade 11 students of Bontoc I and II Districts in Southern Leyte Division.

The Survey Questionnaire for Teachers. The survey questionnaire for teachers was composed of four parts and used 5-point scale in measurement. Part I is the profile of the teachers. Part II measures the extent to which the topics in English were developed among Grade 11 students in terms of decoding meaning of words through context clues, following directions/ instructions, noting details, getting the main idea, reading comprehension, predicting outcomes, differentiating fact from opinion, evaluating ideas/ making generalization, drawing conclusions, using the library effectively, and skimming and scanning. Moreover, Part III deals with the teaching approaches employed by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11 along Communicative- Based Approach, Process Approach, Experimental Approach and Cooperative Approach. Part IV focuses on the instructional materials utilized in teaching English for Grade 11; printed materials, audio aids, visual aids, audio- visual materials, demonstration, community resource, laboratory, programmed instruction and communicative workouts undertaken in the developmental learning design through rationale, objectives, pre-test, learning design, developmental learning exercise, progress check, feedback in progress check and evaluation. And the last part treats on the problems met by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11.

Validation of Instrument

The reading proficiency test in English for Grade 11 as instrument in this study was validated before the conduct of the data gathering in this study. This was validated to the English teachers who are teaching in Bontoc National High School to ensure the usability of the test to the Grade 11 students. Based on the result of the validation of the instrument it was found out that some items were very easy in which some of the comprehension was change to develop higher order thinking skills development. Then, the researcher prepares for final draft of the reading proficiency test. The test ranges from easy, average, and difficult comprehension. After the final draft, was written the reading proficiency test was administered to Grade 11 students in Bontoc National High School. Since they both belong to the Southern Leyte Division, they share the same vision and mission which is to achieve educational excellence and improve the quality of life.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the conduct of the study, permission was asked from the schools Division Superintendent of Southern, Leyte. Upon permission was granted, the researcher designed instruments after which administered survey questionnaire to the target respondents. Before the conduct of proficiency test an orientation was conducted to the Grade 11 respondents from each respondent school in order to provide them background on the purpose of the study and how to answer it. After the orientation test follow then respondent-teachers were given survey questionnaire. The data gathering was one shot activity. Hence, the researcher was able to finish the test on the same day as the student respondents were identified.

The teacher- related information was obtained through the survey questionnaire that was administered to them by the researcher herself. All the teachers teaching English 11 were made to answer the survey questionnaire. The categories included the extent to which the competencies and skills were taught and developed; and the problems met by teachers in teaching reading.

The first school conducted was Paku National High School then followed by Hilaan National High School, Divisoria National High School and finally Bontoc National High School. The data gathering took two (2) days until it was finished.

The data gathered were tallied, organized, and interpreted with the use of statistical tools in order to come up with the output that is expected to be beneficial to both the teachers and Grade 11 students.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In order to analyze the raw data that was obtained from the data gathering procedures, appropriate statistical tools were used.

The descriptive statistics such as percentage and the weighted mean were utilized in order to analyze and interpret the data gathered.

The mean values and their qualitative description used in analyzing and interpreting data was patterned from the study conducted by Sudario (2018).

To find the percentage, the following formula was used:

$$M = \frac{\sum TS}{N} \times 100\%$$

Where: M = mean

$\sum TS$ = sum of weighted average

N = number of cases or respondents

To determine the proficiency level of the Grade 11 students, the mean percentage score (MPS) in the proficiency test was computed using this percentage value and qualitative description as indicated in the DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2015.

PERCENTAGE VALUES

QUALITATIVE DESCRIPTIONS

90 % and above

Advanced (A)

85% - 89%

Proficient (P)

80% - 84%

Approaching Proficiency (AP)

75% - 79%

Developing (D)

74% - below

Beginning (B)

To describe the extent to which the least learned competencies in English were developed among the Grade 11 students, the following values and qualitative descriptions were used:

MEAN VALUES	QUALITATIVE DESCRIPTIONS
3.50 – 4.00	Extensively Developed
2.50 – 3.49	Developed
1.50 – 2.49	Poorly Developed
1.00 – 1.49	Not Developed

To identify the extent to which the instructional materials were used by the teachers in English for Grade 11, the following mean values and qualitative descriptive were used:

MEAN VALUES	QUALITATIVE DESCRIPTION
3.50 – 4.00	Always Used
2.50 – 3.49	Oftentimes Used
1.50 – 2.49	Sometimes Used
1.00 – 1.49	Never Used

To describe the extent to which the teaching approaches were used by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11, the following mean values and its qualitative interpretations were used:

MEAN VALUES	INTERPRETATION
3.50 – 4.00	Always Used
2.50 – 3.49	Oftentimes Used
1.50 – 2.49	Sometimes Used
1.00 – 1.49	Never Used

To determine to what extent are the problems met by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11, the following mean values and its qualitative descriptions were used:

MEAN VALUES	QUALITATIVE DESCRIPTION
3.50 – 4.00	Always a Problem
2.50 – 3.49	Oftentimes a Problem

1.50 – 2. 49

Sometimes a Problem

1.00 – 1.49

Not a Problem

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proficiency Level in English of the Grade 11 Students

Table 2 presents the proficiency level in English for Grade 11 as the respondents of the study.

Table 2. **Proficiency Level in English for Grade 11 Students**

Schools	Mean	Interpretation
1. Paku National High School	78.66%	Developing (D)
2. Hilaan National High School	78.33%	Developing (D)
3. Divisoria National High School	78%	Developing (D)
4. Bontoc National High School	79.23%	Developing (D)
Average	78.55%	Developing (D)

Looking at Table 2, it could be seen that Bontoc National High School got a mean percentage score of 79.23%. Meanwhile, Paku National High School got a mean percentage scores of 78.66% and Hilaan National High School got a mean percentage score of 78.33% and Divisoria National High School got a mean percentage scores of 78% with an average mean percentage score of 78.55%, all interpreted as *Developing*.

Data revealed that the Grade 11 students have Satisfactory Performance in English which implies that their reading proficiency needs to be improved. Thus, the Worktext in Reading Skills Development is to be developed and utilized in teaching English.

Cabelin (2009), which developed instructional materials which help, developed the vocabulary development of the Grade 2 pupils. Same as the present study which developed instructional materials which help developed the communicative competence of the Grade 11 students.

Regis (2008), which designed work text in reading for the improvement of the reading ability of the Grade 4 pupils. The same as the present study which develop Worktext in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11 which is a spur towards the progress of the competencies in reading.

Extent to Which the Least Learned Competencies in English Were Developed by the Grade 11 Students

Table 3 presents the topics developed by the Grade 11 students as perceived by the teachers.

It could be gleaned that topics in English for Grade 11 like decoding meaning of words through dictionary/ context clues got a mean score of 2.78. On following directions/ instructions the mean score was 3.04, on noting details, got a mean score of 2.75, on getting the main idea, got the mean score of 3.09, on reading comprehension, got a mean score of 2.95, on predicting outcomes, got the mean score while reading comprehension aspect m of 3.31, on differentiating fact from opinion, got the mean score of 3.18, on evaluating ideas/ making generalization, got the mean score of 3.15, on drawing conclusions, got the mean score of 3.17, on using library effectively, got the mean score of 2.98, and on skimming and scanning, got the mean score of 2.93, all interpreted as *Developed*.

This further suggest that though identified reading skills were very satisfactorily developed among the Grade 11 students, this still needs further enhancement in order to meet the highest standard of learning. Hence, factors affecting the reading skills and abilities of the students should be overcome by the students and teachers themselves.

Renomeron (2009), developed program text as instructional materials in teaching English for Grade 1. Results of the study revealed that the Grade 1 teachers and pupils need these types of instructional materials the same with development of communicative-based instructional materials as the Grade 11 teachers and students need also for the improvement of the achievement level of the Grade 11 students.

Cabelin (2009), developed instructional materials for building vocabulary development for Grade 2 pupils the same with the present study that worktext in reading skills development Grade 11 need to be developed as one of the instructional tools in developing topics for the subject.

Table 3. Extent To Which the Least Learned Competencies in English Were Developed by the Grade 11 Students

Competencies	Mean	Interpretation
1. Decoding meaning of words through dictionary/context clues	2.78	Developed
2. Following directions/ instructions	3.04	Developed
3. Noting details	2.75	Developed
4. Getting the main idea	3.09	Developed
5. Reading comprehension	2.95	Developed
6. Predicting outcomes	3.31	Developed

7. Differentiating fact from opinion	3.18	Developed
8. Evaluating ideas/ making generalization	3.15	Developed
9. Drawing conclusions	3.17	Developed
10. Using the library	2.98	Developed
11. Skimming and scanning	2.93	Developed
Average	3.03	Developed

Extent to Which the Teaching Approaches Were Used by the Teachers in Teaching English for Grade 11

This part presents the teaching approaches employed by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11.

Table 4. Extent to which the Teaching Approaches were used by the Teachers in Teaching English for Grade 11

Teaching Approaches	Mean	Interpretation
1. Process Approach	2.50	Oftentimes Used
2. Discovery Approach	2.50	Oftentimes Used
3. Experimental Approach	2.51	Oftentimes Used
4. Cooperative Approach	3.11	Oftentimes Used
Average	2.66	Oftentimes Used

From the foregoing data, it could be deduced the teaching approaches in teaching English like: process approach, discovery approach, experimental approach and cooperative approach mean scores were 2.50, 2.50, 2.51, 3.11 and all interpreted as *Oftentimes Used* by the teachers in teaching reading.

This implies that most of the teachers do not utilize the teaching approaches in teaching reading without considering that it is useful for the students to have opportunities to own, manage, monitor and reflect upon their learning enterprise. Moreover, it should be remembered that when inculcating worktext in reading skills development in our formal schooling, teachers should be always bear in minds that the starting point is the learner and respect therefore should be given to the learner autonomy, interest and vision of learning. Hence, the learner and his world can be perceived as resources to be leveraged for classroom teaching and learning.

Data revealed that teachers oftentimes employed the different approaches in teaching English for Grade 11 which signals poor performance of the subject. Data implies that different approaches should be employed among Grade 11 teachers in teaching the subject. Significantly, inclusion of the discussion of these approaches should be made in this study so that proper information should be inculcated to the teachers for quality results.

Extent to Which the Instructional Materials Were Used by the Teachers in Teaching English for Grade 11

Table 5 presents the different instructional materials used by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11.

Table 5. Extent To Which the Instructional Materials Were Used by the Teachers in Teaching English for Grade 11

Instructional Materials	Mean	Interpretation
1. Printed materials	3.56	Always Used
2. Visual aids	3.58	Always Used
3. Audio aids	1.52	Sometimes Used
4. Audio visual aids	1.51	Sometimes Used
5. Demonstration	1.50	Sometimes Used
6. Community resource	1.21	Never Used
7. Laboratory	1.50	Sometimes Used
8. Programmed instruction	2.50	Oftentimes Used
9. Communicative- workouts	2.54	Oftentimes Used
Average	2.16	Sometimes Used

Looking at Table 5, it could be seen that printed materials got a mean score of 3.56 and visual aids, got the mean score of 3.56, all interpreted as *Always Used* instructional materials in teaching English for Grade 11. Instructional materials like: audio aids, audio visual materials, demonstration, community resource, laboratory, programmed instruction and communicative workouts, got a mean score of 1.52, 1.51, 1.50, 1.21, 1.50, 2.50, and 2.54 respectively, all interpreted as *Sometime Uesd*. Meanwhile, communicative-workouts got a mean score of 2.54 which was interpreted as *Sometimes Used*.

Data shows that instructional materials utilization is indeed crucial on the part of the teachers in teaching English. This implies that teachers seldom use these instructional procedures in building up learning strategy for their daily instructions. Hence, these instructional procedures serve as their guide in incorporating the different reading skills and strategies that will be developed in reading instruction.

In relation to the problems met by the teachers, the table below indicates the different problems met by the teachers in their daily instruction in reading.

The Problems Met by the Teachers in Teaching English for Grade 11

Table 6 presents the different problems met by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11.

Table 6. The Problems Met by the Teachers in Teaching English for Grade 11

Problems Met	Mean	Interpretation
1. No reading comprehension	3.50	Always a problem
2. Poor Study Habits among Grade 11 Students	3.52	Always a problem
3. Inadequate instruction, specific activities, methods, resources for equipment for worktext reading skills development	3.54	Always a problem
4. Lack of textbooks in reading for grade 11 students	3.29	Always a problem
5. Students Absenteeism	3.57	Always a problem
6. Inadequate resource material for reading skills development	3.31	Always a problem
7. Absence of worktext in reading skills development	3.59	Always a problem
Average	3.57	Always a problem

Looking at the table, it could be concluded that problems met like: no reading comprehension, poor study habits among grade 11 students, inadequate instruction, specific activities, methods, resources or equipment for worktext in reading skills development, lack of textbooks in reading for grade 11 students, students absenteeism, in adequate resource material for reading skills development, and absence of worktext in reading skills development got a mean score of 3.50, 2.52, 3.54, 3. 29, 3.57, 3.31, 3.59 respectively, all interpreted as *Always a problem*.

Data shows that these problems affect the poor performance of the students in English for Grade 11 which signals that solicited cooperation among parents, students, and other stakeholders should be done. In order to have immediate solution on the problems met by the teachers in teaching English subject. The results also imply that the teachers and students need more instructional materials in reading. In addition, it implies that instructional materials were very important in teaching and learning process. Worktext as instructional materials helps the teachers in improving their strategies, motivating the pupils, and develop

remedial and reinforcement activities for slow learners and enrichment activities for average and fast learners.

SUMMARY

This study used the descriptive type of research which utilized survey questionnaire and proficiency test in English for Grade 11. It aimed to develop a worktext in reading skills development for Grade 11.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the proficiency level of the Grade 11 students in English?
2. To what extent are the following least learned competencies in English developed among the Grade 11 students?
 - 2.1 Decoding meaning of Words Through Dictionary/ context Clues
 - 2.2 Following Directions/ Instructions
 - 2.3 Noting Details
 - 2.4 Getting the main idea
 - 2.5 Reading comprehension
 - 2.6 Predicting Outcomes
 - 2.7 Differentiating Fact from Opinion
 - 2.8 Evaluating Ideas/ Making Generalization
 - 2.9 Drawing Conclusions
 - 2.10 Using the Library Effectively
 - 2.11 Skimming and Scanning
3. To what extent are the following identified instructional materials used by teachers in teaching Reading for Grade 11:
 - 3.1 Printed Materials
 - 3.2 Audio aids
 - 3.3 Visual aids
 - 3.4 Audio- visual aids
 - 3.5 Demonstration
 - 3.6 Community resource
 - 3.7 Laboratory
 - 3.8 Programmed instruction
4. To what extent are the following identified approaches used by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11?
 - 4.1 Process approach
 - 4.2 Discovery approach
 - 4.3 Experimental approach
 - 4.4 Cooperative approach
5. What are the problems met by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11?

6. What worktext in reading skills development maybe developed based on the finding of the study?

This study involved seven hundred seven Grade 11 students and sixteen teachers teaching English in the four secondary schools in Bontoc I and II Districts in Southern Leyte Division. Essentially paid attention on the Worktext in Reading Skills Development for Grade 11. To realize this, this study went through in determining the proficiency level of the Grade 11 students as perceived by the teachers in terms of decoding meaning of words through dictionary/ context clues, following directions/instructions, noting details, getting the main idea, reading comprehension, predicting outcomes, differentiating facts from opinion, evaluating ideas/ making generalization, drawing conclusions, using the library effectively, and skimming and scanning; the teaching strategies utilized by the teachers in teaching worktext in reading skills development along the following approaches used by the teachers in teaching English for Grade 11; Process Approach, Discovery Approach, Experimental Approach and Cooperative Approach.

Data were tabulated, analyzed and interpreted using appropriate statistical tool, such as frequency count and mean. Hence, this served as the bases in determining the reading skills development for Grade 11 that were developed during the academic year 2019-2020.

FINDINGS

Based on the specific problems of the study, the following findings are presented.

On the proficiency level in Reading of the Grade 11 students of Bontoc I and II Districts in Southern Leyte Division academic year 2019-2020, were on the “Developing” towards reading as reflected by the overall mean percentage score of 78.55%.

The result implies that the Grade 11 students of Bontoc I and II Districts, Southern Leyte Division were having poor performance in Reading, and needs reinforcement activities that will develop and enhance their reading skills. The use of effective teaching strategies should be considered by the teachers in order to uplift the academic performance of the students.

On the extent to which the least learned competencies in English were developed among the Grade 11 students as perceived by the teachers, the reading skills in terms of decoding meaning of words through dictionary/ context clues, following directions/ instruction, noting details, getting the main idea, reading comprehension, predicting outcomes, differentiating fact from opinion, evaluating ideas/ making generalization, drawing conclusions, using the library effectively, and skimming and scanning were interpreted as “Developed” with overall mean of 3.03.

This suggest that though the identified reading skills were developed among the Grade 11 students, this still needs further enhancement in order to meet the highest standard of learning. Hence, factors affecting the reading skills and abilities of the students should be overcome by the students and teachers themselves.

On the extent to which the teaching approaches were used by the teachers in teaching English were interpreted as “Often Used” with overall mean of 2.66.

This implies that most of the teachers do not used the teaching approaches in teaching Reading without considering that it is useful for the students to have the oppurtunities to own, manage, monitor and reflect upon learning enterprise. Moreover, it should be remembered that when inculcating developmental learning in our formal schooling, teachers should always bear in mind that the starting point is the learner and respect therefore, should be given to the learner autonomy, interest and vision of learning. Hence, the learner and his world can be perceived as resources to be leveraged for classroom teaching and learning.

On the extent to which the instructional materials were used by the teachers in teaching English was “Sometimes Used” in the learning strategy in teaching. Moreover, the overall mean of 2.16 interpreted as “Sometimes Used” by the teachers.

This implies that teachers sometimes use this instructional material in building up learning strategy which for their daily instructions. Hence, these instructional materials serve as their guide in incorporating the different reading skills and strategies that will be developed in reading instruction.

On the problems met by teachers, problem in resources or equipment in reading skill development and students’ absenteeism had the highest mean of 3.57 and 3. 59 which were interpreted as “Always a Problem”. This followed by inadequate instruction, specific activities, methods, poor study habits and no reading comprehension had the mean of 3.54, 3.50 and 3.52 which were interpreted as “Always a Problem”.

Furthermore, the overall mean value of the problems met by the teachers had the mean value of 3.57 was interpreted as “Always a Problem”.

This implies that inadequate instruction, specific activities, methods, resources, poor study habits, absenteeism was one of the primary causes for having low academic performance of the students in reading. This further implies that once there is an adequate instruction, this goes with the lack of various reading materials, resources textbooks and the like, hence, there is no innovative knowledge and information or lessons that can be imparted to the students, that is why most of the students do not have the interest to learn because they are looking for a new learning materials which they make them motivated, excited and interested. This also implies that students can learn only by textbooks but also through other instructional learning materials like worktext in reading which can be read and answered by the students in school or at home. The results also imply that the teachers and students need more instructional materials in reading. In addition, it implies that instructional materials are very important in teaching and learning process; it can help the teachers improved their strategies, motivating the students and developed remedial and reinforcement activities for slow learners and enrichment activities for average and fast learners.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were reached.

On the proficiency level of the Grade 11 Students in Bontoc I and II Districts in Southern Leyte Division, Academic Year 2019-2020, all of the four secondary schools were on the *Developing* towards reading. On the extent to which the reading skills development among the Grade 11 students as perceived by the teachers, the reading skills in terms of decoding meaning of words through dictionary/ context clues, following directions/ instruction, noting details, getting the main idea, reading comprehension, predicting outcomes, differentiating fact from opinion, evaluating ideas/ making generalization, drawing conclusions, using the library effectively, and skimming and scanning were “*developed*” On the extent to which learning approaches were utilized by the teachers in teaching reading, the worktext in reading skills development was “*oftentimes used*” by the teachers in teaching English. However, the instructional materials were “*sometimes used*” On the extent to which instructional procedures were undertaken on development learning in teaching reading, all those identified instructional procedures were “*sometimes used*” in the reading skills development.

On the problems met by teachers, problem on inadequate instructions, specific activities, methods, resources or equipment for Worktext in reading skills development was “*always a problem*”. Moreover, lack of printed materials and textbooks in reading for grade 11 students; lack of instructional materials on reading skills development; inadequate resource materials for developmental activities; absence of skills on learning reading in English were also “*always a problem*”. However, lack of materials on reading in English for reading development was “*always a problem*”.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Therefore, it is highly recommended that the worktext in reading skills development for Grade 11 should be designed and utilized in teaching English to improve the achievement level of the Grade 11 students of the secondary schools in the Division of Southern, Leyte.

1. Teachers should adopt the different programs and projects of the Department of Education and look for other interventions in raising the level of performance of their schools in reading
2. A knowledge as well as the use of varied Reading strategies is highly recommended to enable students to learn the different reading competencies for Grade 11.
3. Teachers should use varied instructional materials to help students understand their reading materials.
4. School heads should encourage teachers to attend seminars, trainings, workshops to train them on the different approaches that maybe used in teaching.
5. The use of this worktext in reading skills development for Grade 11 is highly recommended.
6. Similar studies may be conducted in other schools to provide teachers with additional instructional materials.

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